
SCIENCE INSPIRES HISTORY AND THE FUTURE

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Just getting my thoughts together: How my ideas regarding future science are making history come to life for me + How do I get my hands on a book that tells me not just about the last 10,000 years but about the next 10,000?

We start with the construction of so-called imaginary numbers known as Wick rotation (or the circle of i). The imaginary number i equals the square root of negative 1 ($i^2 = -1$). Now visualize a large + sign where the point on the extreme right of the horizontal x-axis is labelled 1, the one on the left of x is -1, the point at the top of the vertical y-axis is i , and that at the bottom of y is $-i$. Instead of visualizing, it's much better to draw a picture with pen and paper because this easily gets confusing. The centre of the + is termed the origin, and counterclockwise rotation about the origin (beginning on the right, and multiplying each quadrant by i) results in: 1 multiplied by i equals i , i multiplied by i equals -1 , -1 multiplied by i equals $-i$, $-i$ multiplied by i equals 1 (then the second cycle begins).

The Wick rotation can be built into the Mobius strips which can be depicted by the BITS or BInary digiT'S of 1 and 0 (the 1's and 0's represent electrical pulses being in on and off states). Uniting two Mobius strips can form a figure-8 Klein bottle which therefore also incorporates Wick rotation. Trillions of each topological figure (Mobius strip or figure-8 Klein bottle) form, respectively, electromagnetism's photon and gravitation's proposed graviton - the photons and gravitons compose, and fill up, all spacetime. When electromagnetism and gravitation interact via what I call vector-tensor-scalar geometry, they can produce all the particles of matter and antimatter in the universe, as well as bosons of the weak and strong nuclear forces and the Higgs boson.

Combining the physics of James Clerk Maxwell, Albert Einstein, and George Yuri Rainich tells us that both electromagnetic and gravitational waves possess retarded components that travel forwards in time and advanced components that travel back in time. The retarded and advanced waves cancel to cause quantum entanglement and thus unite all particles in the universe into a union or entanglement which might be called Quantum Gravity or the Unified Field. Since the retarded and advanced photons and gravitons form a unified field of all

particles in space, the Wick rotation built into the photons and gravitons should likewise produce a unified field where all time is entangled - the entire past, the present, and every part of the future would coexist.

We can compare this coexistence to a DVD where consciousness replaces the DVD-player's laser. Though all time exists at once, our consciousness is only aware of the incredibly limited number of objects and events in our immediate surroundings.

This brings me to the topic of history coming alive for me. If all time exists simultaneously, everything I read about in history books is taking place right now and I'm too dumb to be aware of it. However, knowing that all those things are really happening as I write this is just so exciting! Somebody can go ahead and invent a time machine now, because it will actually have events to go to. How do I get my hands on a book that tells me not just about the last 10,000 years but about the next 10,000?